

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF SEMICONDUCTOR MICROCHIPS IN SOLVING DOLZARB PROBLEMS IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY

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Abstract: Currently, microchips that perform important tasks in the automotive industry are made of semiconductor materials, and chips are important for manufacturers of all electronic devices and gadgets. Electronic device and gadget manufacturers face many challenges in sourcing and remanufacturing semiconductor materials to deliver orders for microcircuits.

Key words: automotive engineering, electronic device, semiconductors, semiconductor microchips, microcircuits.

As a result of scientific and technical progress, the economy and the mechanical engineering industry are developing rapidly. The development of the economy and industry requires serious research on the creation of high-strength, easy-to-use, cheap, precise materials and on increasing the durability of the connection [1-2]. Modern materials science occupies an important place in the study of the composition, structure and properties of material alloys, as well as the relationship between the structure and properties of the material. Metals and semiconductors are the most used materials in our daily life. Semiconductor materials and metals play an important role in the development of human material culture [3-5]. In fact, there is no sector of the economy where semiconductors and metals are not used.

There are conflicting issues in the selection of materials for machine parts and in the technological process of processing them. For example, the details used in the creation of machines and mechanisms that can ensure safe operation for a long time should be cheap, compact, neat, and made of high-quality materials. It

goes without saying that the processing of such materials causes a sharp increase in cost.

In solving such complex engineering problems, materials science and materials science of semiconductors, as well as technology of construction materials, are of great importance.

To date, microchips that perform important tasks in the automotive industry are made of semiconductor materials, and chips are important for manufacturers of all electronic devices and gadgets. Electronic device and gadget makers are facing many challenges in sourcing and remanufacturing semiconductor materials to deliver chip orders, which in turn is delaying car companies' customer service and delivery of cars to their owners. It leads to the creation of artificial barriers by itself. The lack of timely arrival of microchips will force the suspension of some branches of the automotive company. When restarting operations, chipmakers lag behind existing demand due to the fact that it takes more than six months to produce. Therefore, there is a shortage of semiconductor microchips for cars (Figure 1) [6-8].

The shortage of semiconductors is a concern of car manufacturers around the world [9-10]. The lack of such small but irreplaceable details has had serious consequences for car manufacturers. Another example is Volkswagen's plant in Kaluga, which stopped production of cars due to a shortage of semiconductors. Also, the assembly of Volkswagen and Skoda cars was temporarily suspended in Nizhny Novgorod. Most of the world's largest car manufacturers were forced to suspend their factories in Asia, Europe and North America due to the shortage of semiconductors. . These include Ford Motor, Nissan Motor, Toyota Motor, Volkswagen, Honda Motor and Volvo. The US automotive industry warned about the consequences of improper use of microcircuits and asked for help from the government. Asia is speeding up microchip production to reduce semiconductor shortages.

Figure 1. Semiconductor microchips

In addition, it is worth noting that the shortage of containers and delays at Chinese ports are also causing disruptions in production (Figure 2). The shortage of containers has led to delays in the delivery of purchased goods and increased prices. This is four times higher than the usual price. Any additional costs incurred are covered by retailers or result in overpayments by consumers.

Figure 2. Chinese ports

Xulosa qilib aytganda yarimo‘tkazgichlar fizikasi va yarimo‘tkazgichlar materialshunosligiga katta etibor berilishini va bu soxalarni rivojlantirishga katta sarmoyalar ajratish kerakligini ko‘rsatadi. Yarimo‘tkazgichlarning yetishmasligi avtomobil sanoatini tashvishga soladi. Bunday ammo almashtirib bo‘lmaydigan detallarning yetishmasligi avtomobil ishlab chiqaruvchilar uchun jiddiy

oqibatlarni olib keldi.

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